

MARE VAPORUM – A NEW GEOLOGIC MAP. A. Oetting¹, L. Wueller², C. H. van der Bogert², G. Consuma¹, W. Iqbal², J. Carpenter¹, and T. Heyer², ¹European Space Agency, European Space Research and Technology Centre (ESA/ESTEC), Directorate of Human and Robotic Exploration, Keplerlaan 1, 2201 AZ Noordwijk, the Netherlands (Astrid.Oetting@esa.int), ²Institut für Planetologie, Universität Münster, Wilhelm-Klemm-Str. 10, 48149 Münster, Germany.

Introduction: The characterization of lunar regions that are both geologically diverse and rich in resources has experienced increased interest for planned lunar missions. Geologically diverse regions allow researchers to address major scientific questions such as the volcanic evolution of the Moon, the chronology of lunar impacts, and the origin and distribution of volatiles. In addition, these regions also offer valuable opportunities for the development of in-situ resource utilization (ISRU), which will reduce the dependence on Earth for future lunar missions [1].

Mare Vaporum (13.20°N/4.09°E) is a promising target for future exploration, therefore, we present a new geologic map produced at a scale of 1:125,000. The region includes two pyroclastic deposits (Figure 1, *Ipm*) associated with Rima Hyginus and with the southern edge of Mare Vaporum. These deposits exhibit relatively high concentrations of FeO and TiO₂, which indicate the presence of ilmenite (FeTiO₃). Ilmenite-rich regolith is of special interest for ISRU because it may allow the extraction of oxygen and helium-3 [2]. The geologic variety within Mare Vaporum (Figure 1) makes it a compelling region in terms of ISRU for future missions and also provides an opportunity to investigate the volcanic and tectonic history of the Moon.

Method: To distinguish geologic units based on differences in albedo, topography, and morphology, we used images from the Kaguya SELENOlogical and Engineering Explorer (SELENE) Terrain Camera (TC) images, supported by Kaguya TC digital elevation models (DEMs) both with pixel scales of ~10 m/px [3]. In addition, spectral data were used such as the Clementine UVVIS color ratio map [4] and Kaguya Lunar Multiband Imager (MI) maps (i.e., FeO, olivine, orthopyroxene, clinopyroxene, plagioclase [5], and TiO₂ [6]).

Mapping is based on the stratigraphic scheme of [7] and follows the mapping standards described in [8] and in the Planetary Geologic Mapping Protocol [9].

Results: The Mare Vaporum region shows diverse geologic units that are important for interpreting the volcanic and tectonic evolution of the Moon. The exposed materials span from the Nectarian period to the Copernican period.

Terra material (Nt) - An elongated ridge located in the eastern part of the study region, with an uncertain formation process, is interpreted as Nectarian terra material.

Basin material (Nbm, If) - The rim of the Serenitatis basin forms a prominent elevated feature in the northeastern part of the region. The Fra Mauro Formation, which consists of ejecta from the Imbrium impact event, is present in the northern and southern mapping region.

Dark plains material (Idp1, Idp2) - These units have a low albedo and smooth topography. They may represent ancient volcanic plains buried beneath younger materials. Since they lack dark halo craters, a clear classification as cryptomare [10] is not possible. The dark plains units are primarily embayed by the Fra Mauro Formation. They are suggested to be Imbrian in age.

Pyroclastic material (Ipm) - Two significant dark mantling deposits occur in the region: the Mare Vaporum deposit and the Rima Hyginus deposit. The underlying topography remains visible at both deposits. FeO concentrations range from ~15-19 wt%, and the TiO₂ values range from ~2-4 wt%. The pyroclastic eruptions are interpreted to have occurred during the Imbrian period.

Cryptomare material (Imc) - This unit is characterized by low albedo and a smooth topography. The presence of dark halo craters indicates cryptomare [10]. This unit is present in the eastern and southeastern portion of the region and likely formed during the Imbrian period.

Light plains material (Ilp) - High albedo and flat topography characterize this unit. The high albedo is interpreted as the result of emplacement of material produced through impact processes. It is located in the southern part of the mapping area and is Imbrian in age.

Cratered plains material (Ipc) - This unit is slightly darker than the Fra Mauro Formation and has a rougher, more heavily cratered surface. It is located in the southeastern part of the study region and is interpreted as Imbrian in age.

Mare material (Im1-4, Em) - Geologic units with extensive dark and smooth surfaces and moderate TiO₂ and high FeO signatures cover most of the study region. These areas are interpreted as mare basalts and formed during the Imbrian and Eratosthenian periods.

Crater material (Ic, Ec, Cc) - Identified were also materials associated with impact craters, including ejecta blankets, central peaks, crater floors, and impact melt. Only craters with diameters ≥5 km were mapped separately.

Tectonic and volcanic features - The region contains a variety of tectonic and volcanic features, including graben, domes, depressions such as pits and irregular mare patches, and wrinkle ridges. Rima Hyginus (*Ir*) is a large graben partly surrounded by pyroclastic material. Domes, pits, and graben are interpreted as Imbrian in age, while wrinkle ridges formed between the Imbrian and the Eratosthenian periods in the study region. The age of irregular mare patches, such as *Ina*, remains debated, with proposed ages ranging from Imbrian [11] to Copernican [12].

Conclusion: The new geologic map highlights Mare Vaporum as a promising region for future ISRU, particularly because of the pyroclastic deposits enriched in FeO and TiO₂. The broad geologic diversity, which includes highland and basin materials, mare material, light plains, dark plains, and cryptomare, increases the scientific potential for future lunar missions. The presence of domes, pits, and irregular mare patches provides evidence of past volcanic activity and supports the reconstruction of the volcanic history of the region. Analyses of slopes and rock abundance show that the region meets requirements for safe landings.

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Figure 1: Geologic map of the Mare Vaporum region. The mapping scale is 1:125,000.